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Blended higher education in Europe

A review of frameworks and principles for design, quality and maturity

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EMBED+ is a partnership of 5 European Higher Education Institutions. The partnership consists of:

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0. Executive Summary

This systematic review examines the design principles and quality assurance practices that support effective blended practices in higher education. Conducted within the context of the EMBED+ project, the review synthesizes literature published between 2020 and 2025 to understand how blended practices can be designed, supported, and sustained across diverse organisational contexts.

Across the literature, several design principles consistently emerge, including active learning and student engagement, meaningful assessment and feedback, scaffolding, learner autonomy, collaborative and social learning, curricular alignment, motivational and inclusive design, and real-world relevance supported by appropriate technology integration. At the organizational level, studies emphasize the role of sustained professional development, leadership commitment, coordinated support structures, and continuous cycles of evaluation and improvement.

Collectively, this body of work indicates that technology is most effective when it is purposefully embedded to enhance interaction, flexibility, and personalized learning, rather than functioning as a driver of educational design in its own right. Quality assurance and maturity practices are less consistently addressed in the literature but remain critical for scalability and sustainability. Evidence suggests that institutions benefit from embedding quality processes throughout the lifecycle of blended education (planning, design, delivery, and evaluation) supported by frameworks, accessible data, and feedback mechanisms.

Overall, the review provides a consolidated evidence base for strengthening blended practices in higher education. It shows that effective blended education is a whole-institution endeavor requiring continuous quality improvement. These findings inform the ongoing development of the EMBED+ project, including the renewed maturity model, the maturity matrix and its resources hub. It offers as well actionable insights for educators, researchers, and policymakers aiming to advance blended practices in higher education.

1. Introduction

1.1. From emergency remote teaching to blended practices

The COVID-19 pandemic has profoundly transformed the landscape of tertiary education across European higher education institutions (HEIs). The abrupt shift from on-site teaching to “emergency remote teaching” (ERT) exposed systemic vulnerabilities, including unequal access to technology, inconsistent instructional quality, and a decline in student engagement (Hodges et al., 2020). While this emergency response was far from optimal, it served as a catalyst for institutional innovation and the reconfiguration of teaching and learning practices.

A key development emerging from this disruption has been the normalization of blended practices. While there remains ambiguity about the scope and core conceptions (Smith & Hill, 2019), in this study blended learning is defined as “learning as a result of a deliberate, integrated combination of online and face-to-face learning activities.” Blended teaching, accordingly, is understood as “designing and facilitating blended learning activities.” Here, “deliberate” underscores the explicit role of instructional design in sequencing online and face-to-face components, while “integrated combination” highlights the rationale for selecting blends of digital and physical learning spaces (Goeman & Dijkstra, 2022).

The pandemic accelerated the adoption of these blended practices. Initially adopted out of necessity, they have since evolved into more strategic and sustainable models, with institutions recognizing the flexibility, accessibility, and continuity that blended formats provide (Vlachopoulos, 2022). Among others, Baldassarre et al. (2021) demonstrate how ERT accelerated the exploration of blended formats in Italian universities. Bidarra et al. (2024) describe this as a “strong push” toward digital technologies and instructional design, marking the pandemic as a turning point in higher education’s digital transformation. Although precise data on the extent of implementation are limited, the trajectory suggests that hybrid and blended models are now integral to the future of European higher education.

1.2. Developments in technology, pedagogy, and social dimensions

The pandemic triggered significant technological advances that reshaped program delivery. Online learning platforms became central to course delivery, enabling both synchronous and asynchronous instruction. Advanced collaboration tools allowed for real-time feedback and group work, replicating interactive classroom elements. Emerging technologies such as artificial intelligence (AI) and immersive virtual environments offered new possibilities for simulation-based and experiential learning, while digital assessment systems provided scalable solutions for remote evaluation. Learning analytics further enabled personalized pathways by identifying at-risk students and tailoring content to individual needs (Lee et al., 2024). The growth of open

educational resources (OER) also enriched blended formats by providing customizable materials for integration across modalities.

These innovations enhanced flexibility, but they also exposed infrastructural and pedagogical challenges. Hardware limitations, insufficient internet bandwidth, and uneven quality of digital tools hindered effective implementation (Bidarra et al., 2024).

Furthermore, the rapid transition revealed gaps in digital literacy among both students and staff (Mitescu-Manea et al., 2021). Ensuring quality required not only technical integration, but also significant organizational and cultural shifts within HEIs. Universities faced pressure to accommodate diverse populations, address digital poverty, and compete with large technology providers while upholding academic values.

From a pedagogical perspective, the pandemic reinforced the centrality of purposeful instructional design. Beyond technological availability, effective blended teaching relies on the intentional orchestration of modalities, encompassing course structure and pacing, pedagogical activity design, and the teacher's role in fostering engagement and relational dynamics (Heilporn et al., 2021). As a result, institutions revisited course design principles to prioritize learner-centred and evidence-informed approaches. Teachers increasingly assumed roles as facilitators, enablers, and co-learners rather than traditional knowledge transmitters (Homanen, 2021). Social and psychological dimensions also became central. Online wellbeing emerged as a critical issue, with scholars noting risks related to surveillance, algorithmic biases, and digital inequality that could exacerbate stress and exclusion (Bidarra et al., 2024). Concepts such as “positive computing” (Sander, 2010), “positive technology” (Riva et al., 2012), and “positive design” (Faust, 2009) informed efforts to create supportive environments for emotional and academic wellbeing, extending the framework of positive psychology (Seligman & Csikszentmihalyi, 2000). Recent contributions highlight “positive technologies for learning” (Heutte, 2021; Molinari et al., 2022) as promising avenues for sustaining motivation and wellbeing in hybrid contexts.

Capacity building has likewise proven indispensable. Educators need training to select and use pedagogically meaningful tools, while students must acquire digital skills to navigate hybrid systems effectively (Do, 2024; Karpava, 2022). Evidence suggests that although students valued the flexibility of online and asynchronous learning, many continued to prefer face-to-face teaching for its social, interactive, and cognitive benefits (Karpava, 2022). Still, student perceptions are mixed: Romanian studies reported that many students found online formats more effective than on-site education (Ionescu & Stan, 2022; Maier et al., 2020), while Austrian and Macedonian studies showed limited preference for a full return to campus (Andreeski et al., 2023). A German study found that online participation did not negatively impact grades or motivation and that students who preferred online study should not be stereotyped as unmotivated (Schmälzle & Berkling, 2023). These findings highlight the diversity of learner needs and the importance of offering multiple pathways.

The experiences of national systems reinforce this trend. Swedish universities invested in digital infrastructure and explored new pedagogical models such as virtual laboratories and interactive platforms (Dafgård & Creelman, 2021), while Finland adopted remote and hybrid modes as viable

long-term solutions (Lehto & Engblom-Pelkkala, 2021). Such initiatives demonstrate the enduring structural changes set in motion by the pandemic.

Some literature indicates a widespread adoption of blended practices across European HEIs. A survey by the European University Association (EUA) confirmed that blended teaching has become mainstream across European universities, supported by both institutional strategies and European Union (EU) or national funding (Gaebel et al., 2021). Other research syntheses highlight broader patterns. Dikilitaş and Rambla (2022), for example, identify significant policy developments in France, Norway, Poland, Portugal, and Spain, underlining how diverse contexts have embraced blended models. The OECD's "Education Working Paper No. 281" (Staring et al., 2022) further categorizes EU member states by their approaches to external quality assurance (QA) in digital higher education.

The report distinguishes between countries with specific QA standards, those with general standards applicable to all delivery modes, and those lacking evidence of QA frameworks for blended or digital education. It also clarifies the distinctions between online, hybrid, and blended modalities (Staring et al., 2022).

1.3. Future directions and policy making

The pandemic underscored the need for systemic investment and policy reform to support blended education. Effective implementation depends on robust infrastructure, comprehensive professional development, and inclusive access to technologies (Bidarra et al., 2024). Equally critical are ethical frameworks for data use and QA systems that ensure consistency across modalities. By facilitating the exchange of good practices among institutions and countries, policy frameworks can help build a more coherent European Higher Education Area (EHEA).

Sustained innovation will require universities to balance traditional academic values with digital transformation. Scholars note the growing permanence of online and blended education, emphasizing the need to move beyond a "classroom-first" approach (Niinivaara & Nelson, 2023). Intelligent hybrid classrooms, co-teaching models, and investment in pedagogical capacity are key strategies for future growth (Schmälzle & Berkling, 2023; Amarasinghe et al., 2024). Supporting faculty through collaborative platforms such as the proposed "Lecturer Satchel" can further strengthen digital capacity and foster open educational practices (Wahls et al., 2022).

Student engagement remains a central concern. Teachers report difficulties maintaining interaction in digital settings (Meylani, 2024), highlighting the importance of integrating social and participatory elements into hybrid formats. While online platforms provide convenience, maintaining community and dialogue is vital to sustaining motivation. Blended practices, when designed deliberately and inclusively, can address this challenge by combining the best of physical and digital environments.

Ultimately, the experience of emergency remote teaching has positioned European HEIs to become more adaptive and learner-centred. The post-pandemic period represents an opportunity to embed blended education as a core institutional mission, thereby strengthening

resilience against future disruptions (Pellegrini et al., 2020). By fostering cultures of continuous innovation, digital literacy, and inclusivity, European universities can ensure that blended education supports equitable access to high-quality learning opportunities for diverse student populations (Vlachopoulos, 2022).

1.4. Key policies affecting blended education and teaching in Europe

Higher education in Europe is not governed by a single, harmonized policy framework. Instead, general views, guidelines, and recommendations are developed at the EU level, while individual member states retain substantial autonomy to shape their higher education missions, governance, and operational strategies. Since 2020, however, the COVID-19 pandemic has accelerated the adoption of blended forms of education, pushing both EU institutions and national governments to devise strategies, legislation, and funding mechanisms that modernize and digitalize higher education.

The following paragraphs explore the key EU-level initiatives, national policies, and cross-border developments that have shaped the trajectory of blended higher education in Europe post-2020. These underscore that blended education is no longer peripheral but is increasingly embedded into national and institutional strategies. The drivers are both top-down - through EU and government funding, frameworks, and legislation - and bottom-up, via institutional innovation and academic communities of practice.

1.4.1. EU-level initiatives and strategies

One of the most significant post-2020 strategies is the “Digital Education Action Plan 2021–2027” (DEAP), which represents a cornerstone of EU policy for digital transformation in education. DEAP emphasizes the creation of a high-performing digital education ecosystem across Europe, prioritizing flexible, hybrid, and blended teaching environments while also supporting enhanced digital skills and competences (European Commission, 2020). Key elements of this plan include ethical guidelines for AI and data use in education, digital literacy for combating disinformation, and cross-national collaboration to foster innovation.

Closely aligned with DEAP, the “European Strategy for Universities” articulates a vision for strengthening the European Education Area by 2030. It explicitly supports blended teaching models, promotes the adaptation of universities to technological and societal change, and encourages inclusion and transnational partnerships (European Commission, 2022). In parallel, the Council of the European Union issued a “Recommendation on blended learning” in 2021. While this recommendation primarily addressed primary and secondary education, it nevertheless reflects wider EU recognition of blended practices in formal education (Council of the European Union, 2021).

Funding instruments have played a critical role. The “Recovery and Resilience Facility” (RRF), a central component of the EU’s pandemic recovery, has allowed member states to channel

resources into digital infrastructure, curriculum innovation, and professional development, thereby accelerating the implementation of blended and hybrid practices in higher education (European Commission, 2021). For instance, RRF resources have been used for micro-credentials, online training, and the upskilling of academic staff (European Commission, 2020).

The EU has also supported more targeted projects. The DigiTel project (2020–2022), funded by Erasmus+, exemplifies efforts to develop online, blended, and hybrid education using the EMBED framework. It created cross-institutional courses, showcasing how shared pedagogical frameworks can facilitate consistent quality standards in blended education. Other initiatives include digital inclusion programs for students with disabilities, rural learners, or socioeconomically disadvantaged groups. The “European Universities Initiative” has similarly promoted blended and virtual exchange models, expanding international mobility in digital forms (European Commission, 2023).

To monitor progress, the EU has encouraged the uptake of benchmarking tools such as “DigCompEdu” and “HEInnovate”, which provide systematic assessments of institutional digital maturity and innovative practices in blended education (Redecker & Punie, 2017; European Commission, 2023). These tools are increasingly influential in aligning institutional strategies with European priorities.

Finally, cross-border cooperation initiatives, particularly under the “Interreg France-Wallonie-Vlaanderen programme”, illustrate how regional partnerships can reinforce digital higher education. Projects such as “Dig-e-Lab” (2016–2020), “Teach Transition” (2020–2023), and “Open Badge for IT” (2024–2028) demonstrate ongoing commitment to digital innovation, teacher training, and lifelong learning through shared resources across Belgian and French universities.

1.4.2. National policy developments in European member states

While EU strategies set the tone, national governments have developed diverse approaches to embedding blended practices into higher education. In Flanders (Belgium), the “Voorsprongfonds Hoger Onderwijs” (2021–2023) formed part of the “Vlaamse Veerkracht” recovery plan. Supported by €60 million - of which €53.8 million was financed via the RRF - the fund targeted modernization and resilience in higher education, with a strong emphasis on blended and digital practices (Department of Education and Training, n.d.).

France has prioritized blended and hybrid education through its “France 2030” strategy, which includes substantial funding for EdTech innovation. The “Hybridation des formations de l’enseignement supérieur” program, launched in 2020 as part of the “Programme d’investissements d’avenir (PIA)”, affected over 350,000 students by 2023–2024 (République Française, 2021). Similarly, Germany expanded its “Digitalpakt Schule” to higher education, investing in digital infrastructure and faculty training (Bundesministerium für Bildung und Forschung, 2021).

Italy's "Piano Nazionale di Ripresa e Resilienza (PNRR)" also directed substantial funding toward modernizing higher education, expanding digital competences, and ensuring wider access to blended pathways (Governo Italiano, 2021). The Netherlands, in turn, launched the "Versnellingsplan Onderwijsinnovatie met ICT" (2019–2022), a four-year acceleration plan aimed at embedding blended teaching as standard practice in universities. This initiative, coordinated by the Dutch SURF cooperative with higher education associations, promoted flexible pathways, modular design, and hybrid teaching while linking blended learning to labor-market relevance and micro-credentials (Versnellingsplan, 2020). The versnellingsplan was succeeded by NPuls (<https://npuls.nl>). This programme was funded from the National Growth Fund with 384,7 million euros and aims to "improve the quality of education, increase the flexibility and accessibility of education, and improve the digital skills of learners and educators" (Npuls, 2025 or <https://www.nationaalgroeifonds.nl/overzicht-lopende-projecten/thema-onderwijs/digitaliseringsimpuls-onderwijs-nl>). This programme runs from 2023 till 2030 and involves multiple universities, universities of applied sciences and vocational education institutions in the Netherlands.

Northern Europe offers further examples of policy mainstreaming. Finland's "Digivisio 2030" program seeks to create a unified digital learning environment across higher education institutions, backed by national quality standards for blended education (Finnish Ministry of Education and Culture, 2022; Digivisio 2030, 2022). Estonia has similarly integrated blended teaching principles into its QA standards (Estonian Education and Youth Board, 2021). Ireland and Portugal have also introduced formal definitions and guidelines for blended course design, reinforcing consistency in quality assurance (MCTES, 2020; National Forum for the Enhancement of Teaching and Learning in Higher Education, 2021). Complementing these formal strategies, a few policy studies have influenced debates. For example, Boland and Hazelkorn (2022) emphasize that sustainability and competitiveness in Irish higher education depend on strategic investment in digital capacity and staff development. Their propositions - although nationally focused - resonate across European contexts.

1.5. Rationale of the EMBED+ project

In sum, the COVID-19 pandemic has served as a critical accelerant for the normalization of blended higher education. What began as a reactive shift has gradually evolved into a reconfiguration of pedagogical approaches. This transformation has led to a reorientation of institutional and policy priorities toward more learner-centred, digitally enabled, and adaptable education systems. In the post-2020 era, higher education policy across Europe has clearly transitioned from a short-term crisis response to a more long-term strategic plan.

At both EU and national levels, legislative and funding frameworks increasingly support digital transformation, pedagogical innovation, and equitable access to quality learning opportunities. These developments reflect a shared vision for the future of the EHEA. Nevertheless, significant challenges remain, particularly in translating high-level policy objectives into effective institutional practices that can be scaled and sustained across diverse contexts.

Building on the lessons learned during the pandemic, the current educational landscape presents a critical opportunity to fundamentally reimagine higher education through the systematic integration of blended models and practices. This moment demands a transition from ad hoc solutions to structured, evidence-informed strategies that enhance blended teaching and learning across European HEIs. The European Maturity Model for Blended Education Plus (EMBED+) project responds directly to this need. Leveraging the collective expertise of its consortium partners, EMBED+ aims to strengthen the blended education ecosystem throughout European HEIs.

Building on the original EMBED project, EMBED+ aims to develop a refined European Maturity Model (EMM), practical self-assessment tools, and an open-access hub to guide institutions in enhancing the design, delivery, and QA of blended teaching and education. Ultimately, it seeks to ensure that blended education becomes a lasting and transformative feature of European higher education.

Figure 1
Overview of the EMBED+ project

EMBED+ consists of five work packages (WPs), each focusing on different key aspects of the project.

In particular, the project entails: (1) project management including the coordination of project activities, budget and resource management, partner communication and quality assurance; (2) use and needs analysis (3) model development, (4) development and integration of an open-source EMBED+ Hub, i.e. a hybrid platform/repository providing materials; (5) communication and dissemination, focused on organising an EU roadshow and establishing a transnational expert network for ongoing professional development.

The EMBED+ project comprises three research strands (see Figure 1, highlighted in red). The first, the systematic use case assessment, focuses on analysing the uptake and use of deliverables from the original EMBED project in HEIs across Belgium and the Netherlands. Central to the second research strand is the development and validation of the foundations of a new maturity model. A key component is a systematic review of scientific and professional literature (SRS) published between 2020 and 2025, which provides a comprehensive evidence base to inform the model's design. This SRS is conducted alongside a Delphi study. The third strand involves piloting the EMBED+ Hub to evaluate its implementation and usability within HEIs, ensuring that the project's outcomes are both evidence-informed and practically grounded.

This report presents the outcomes of the systematic review and is structured into four sections. The first section outlines the review's objectives, the second describes the methodological approach, including the search strategies, selection criteria, and data analysis procedures. The subsequent section presents the findings of the review, followed by the key implications for the further development of the EMBED+ model.

1.6. Focus of the systematic review study

Blended teaching requires stakeholders to align didactical strategies with learner characteristics and learning outcomes while deliberately leveraging the complementary affordances of online and face-to-face modalities. As Kerres and De Witt (2003) emphasize, a coherent and unified instructional design is central to shaping blended teaching environments that foster meaningful engagement and improved educational outcomes. The COVID-19 pandemic further underscored the importance of adaptable design principles capable of ensuring a seamless transition between onsite and remote learning formats.

Such adaptability is essential not only for maintaining educational continuity during crises (Williams et al., 2022), but also for sustaining resilience in the longer term. Taken together, these challenges highlight that the design of blended courses and programs is a highly complex and demanding endeavour. In response to these complexities, increasing attention has been directed not only to the design of blended teaching but also to the frameworks and standards through which its quality and effectiveness can be evaluated. Building on this perspective, recent developments highlight the need to reconsider how blended teaching environments are designed and evaluated. In the post-COVID-19 landscape, organizations such as the European Association for Quality Assurance in Higher Education (ENQA) have updated their criteria to reflect the growing importance of digital and blended formats (ENQA, 2022).

Against this backdrop, the first area of focus in this study is the identification of key design principles and evidence-informed practices published between 2020 and 2025. These insights aim to inform the development of effective blended environments within HEIs. The second focus centres on standards and frameworks designed to evaluate and enhance the quality and maturity of blended practices.

While QA models focus on validating and maintaining predefined quality levels, maturity assessment (MA) models gauge the developmental stage of processes or practices, guiding strategic growth and organizational development. Both are valuable but serve different objectives within educational contexts.

To guide this investigation, the following research questions were formulated:

1. *What design principles and best practices are commonly used to ensure the effectiveness of blended courses and programs?*
2. *What standards and frameworks exist for evaluating and improving the quality and maturity of blended learning practices in higher education?*

2. Method

2.1. General study design

The systematic review aimed to examine the recent body of literature on blended education and teaching. This study employed a systematic review methodology, as outlined by Cherry et al. (2023), to ensure methodological integrity while synthesizing key insights from current research:

1. The search and identification of studies begins with the development of a search strategy to identify relevant literature. This typically involves selecting appropriate databases, and using well-defined search terms, including Boolean operators to combine concepts and asterisks to capture variations of a word, such as "blended educat*" to include "blended education" and "blended educational practices." Inclusion and exclusion criteria are then applied to filter studies.
2. Screening, selection and data extraction involve reviewing studies through multiple stages: initial screening of titles and abstracts to eliminate irrelevant articles, followed by full-text screening and assessment of the quality and rigor of the studies. Relevant data and key findings are extracted for analysis.
3. Finally, the findings are then synthesized thematically to answer the research questions, summarizing evidence from the studies.

2.2. Search and identification strategies

To gather relevant scientific studies and reports, keyword searches were conducted in major academic databases, namely ERIC, Web of Science (Clarivate Analytics), EBSCO and SCOPUS (Elsevier). Table 1 presents the keywords that are used in each of the search queries to retrieve literature related to blended higher education.

Table 1.
Keywords used in search queries

English Keyword
Blended learn*
Hybrid learn*
Blended educat*
Blended teaching
Hybrid teaching
Higher education
University*
Tertiary education

Note: The asterisk (*) indicates truncation used in the search strategy.

The successful design of blended courses and programs required careful consideration of principles to ensure that learning outcomes are optimized. The following search strategies were employed to investigate which design principles are being applied in higher education to achieve this goal:

("blend" OR "hybrid*") AND ("course*" OR "program*") AND ("design principles" OR "design model" OR "design guidelines") AND ("effectiveness") AND ("higher education" OR "university*" OR "tertiary education")*

Assessing and enhancing the quality or maturity of blended practices is important for institutions looking to improve their offerings continuously. While a QA model primarily aims to ensure that processes, courses, or programs meet predefined quality standards, a MA model focuses on evaluating the developmental sophistication or maturity level of processes or practices over time. To identify frameworks or models that are used for this purpose, the following search is conducted:

("blended learn" OR "hybrid learn*" OR "blended educat*" OR "blended teaching" OR "hybrid teaching") AND ("quality" OR "maturity") AND ("assess*" OR "evaluat*") AND ("higher education" OR "university*" OR "tertiary education") AND ("model*" OR "framework*")*

The review period looks back to January 2020 through to February 2025¹, when the sample is constructed. The inclusion and exclusion criteria are developed to ensure that the studies selected for analysis align with the research objectives and meet a standardized methodological quality (Tables 2a and 2b). For the review, both scientific studies and grey literature or professional reports are selected, screened, and examined. For scientific studies, only peer-reviewed articles, conference papers, and dissertations are considered, with a focus on empirical studies using qualitative, quantitative, or mixed methods. The studies must specifically address blended education or blended teaching. For grey and professional literature, only reports published by educational institutions, government agencies, and professional organizations are considered. Relevant sources include conference proceedings, white papers, and professional journals or magazines that discuss blended practices, trends, and outcomes in higher education.

¹ The filtering options in ERIC, WoS and SCOPUS for time frame 2020-2025 were applied in the search or advanced search of the databases.

Table 2a.

Inclusion criteria for the systematic review of scientific, grey and professional literature

Scientific studies	Gray and professional literature
Study types	Types of resources
Peer-reviewed articles, conference papers, and dissertations. Empirical studies (qualitative, quantitative, multi-method or mixed method). Literature reviews and meta-analyses.	Reports from educational institutions, government agencies, professional organizations or non-profit organizations related to blended education and teaching. Conference proceedings and presentations that may not be published in journals. White papers or position papers from educational associations. Articles from professional journals or magazines focused on education, technology, or pedagogy.
Educational context	Relevance
Research focusing specifically on blended education or blended teaching. Studies addressing higher education levels (undergraduate, graduate, postgraduate, PhD).	Documents that discuss blended practices, trends, challenges, or outcomes in higher education. Content that provides evidence-informed practices, case studies, or expert opinions on blended education in higher education. Case studies or evaluations of blended education projects in European institutions.
Time frame	Time frame
Publications published from 2020 onward.	Publications published from 2020 onward.
Language	Language
Articles published in English.	Articles published in English.

Table 2a.

Inclusion criteria for the systematic review of scientific, grey and professional literature

Scientific studies	Gray and professional literature
Study types	Quality standards
Non-peer-reviewed articles, opinion pieces, editorials, and book chapters. Studies that do not present empirical data or clear methodologies.	Non-credible or unverifiable sources, such as personal blogs or opinion pieces without substantiated evidence. Literature lacking clear methodologies or rigorous evaluation. Professional literature that lacks rigorous editorial standards.

Table 2a - Continued

Scientific studies	Gray and professional literature
Educational context Research focused on K-12 education, vocational training, or non-higher education settings.	Irrelevant topics/content Outdated reports or studies that do not provide current insights. Articles that primarily present opinions, marketing content, or promotional materials without data or rigorous analysis. Publications that do not explicitly relate to blended education or teaching, or that focus on unrelated educational methodologies, or do not focus on higher education contexts.
Time frame Publications prior to 2020, unless they are foundational works directly relevant to the topic.	
Language Articles not published in English.	

2.3. Screening and selection

The review process began with the setup of a computer-based collaborative review management environment (Covidence), providing a structured approach to organizing the entire review process. This platform was used to support study screening, data extraction, and overall review management. A pilot test involving the whole research team was conducted to assess the effectiveness of the search queries and data extraction procedures. Once the relevant studies were retrieved, the next step involved an initial screening of titles and abstracts. This helped eliminate irrelevant studies based on their topic, objectives, and context. A full-text review was then conducted to verify that the selected studies met the inclusion criteria in greater detail. To guide the study selection process and ensure transparency, the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses (PRISMA) framework was used (Page et al., 2021), including a flow diagram that visually illustrates the stages from study identification to final inclusion of scientific studies, next to resources from grey and professional literature (see Figures 2a, 2b, 3a and 3b).

2.4. Extraction and synthesis of data

Once the studies have been selected, the next phase involves extracting relevant data. For each study, key information is systematically extracted. The extraction table serves as a structured tool for organizing and analyzing data from each study. During data collection, relevant information was carefully extracted and recorded in the table to ensure consistency in summarizing and categorizing results. As the review progressed, the tables allowed for cross-referencing, helping to identify recurring themes and patterns across studies, which aided in answering the research questions and synthesizing in a narrative manner.

Additionally, the extraction tables facilitated a critical evaluation of existing research, highlighting methodological approaches, findings, and limitations. The extraction tables are presented in the Appendices.

Figure 2a

PRISMA Flow Diagram for the Scientific Studies about Blended Course and Programme Design

Figure 2b

PRISMA Flow Diagram for the Grey and Professional Literature about Blended Course and Programme Design

Figure 3a
PRISMA Flow Diagram for the Scientific Studies on QA and MA

Figure 3b
PRISMA Flow Diagram for the Grey and Professional Literature on QA and MA

3. Results

3.1. What design principles and best practices are commonly used to ensure the effectiveness of blended courses and programs?

3.1.1. Active learning and engagement

In Alejandro Armellini's 2018 publication, "The large lecture (theatre) is dead...", he advocates for the replacement of traditional lectures with "active blended learning", a method that combines on-campus and online learning activities, resulting in participatory and student-centred learning. This approach encourages students to actively engage with course materials, connect with their prior knowledge, and reflect on learning activities to achieve deep processing. Empirical evidence suggests a positive relationship between active teaching strategies and students' engagement (Arjomandi et al., 2018).

Results from studies included in this SRS indicate that active sequences raise learner participation and performance. For example, in a longitudinal study conducted by Olmedo-Torre et al. (2020) four active learning strategies were used to test the effectiveness of blended instructional design on an engineering course. These were namely flipped classroom (FC), design thinking, visual thinking and project-based learning (PBL). The results showed that using these four active learning strategies resulted in better student performance and satisfaction overall. The FC method fostered higher engagement with self-assessment tasks which led to improved performance and pass rates, while PBL was most appreciated by the students, yielding the highest grades. Overall, the students reported high levels of satisfaction with active learning indicating increased motivation, clarity and depth of learning.

Kritzinger et al. 's (2021) study examined the impact of a redesigned blended course in first-year biology at a South African university. The redesign, a FC, aimed to improve student performance, learning experiences, and engagement. In the face-to-face tutorials clickers and peer instruction were used to promote active learning. They sought to investigate the differences in engagement with learning opportunities between three groups of students (likely-to-pass, 'murky middle' and at risk) as well as the learning opportunities that correlate with performance. It was found that the blended redesign improved academic performance, especially for low- and mid-performing students. Students reported greater engagement and valued the flexibility and continuous feedback offered by the FC structure.

Duan et al. (2024) applied the "Teaching Objective, Activation, Multi-learning, Assessment, and Summary" model for blended clinical nursing education and found enhanced learner engagement. Olmedo-Torre et al. (2021) reported significant gains from applying four different active-learning strategies in an engineering graphic expression course; Sosa Díaz et al. (2021)

and Yorganci (2020) showed higher interaction and satisfaction with flipped approaches grounded in a *First Principles of Instruction* design. Pertuz et al. (2023) leveraged Massive Open Online Course (MOOC)-based flipped formats in engineering and Scott et al. (2020) improved first-year academic writing via four active learning interventions: interactive writing modules, online discussion forums, out-of-class writing tutorials, and in and out-of-class verbal feedback. In health/professional contexts, Sun et al. (2023) and Guo et al. (2024) used structured pre-class work plus interactive sessions to sustain engagement.

Figure 4
BOPPPS and blended teaching in a course (Hu et al., 2025)

Active learning strategies were also used across other studies, with a focus on student participation and engagement through FCs collaborative tasks, and multimedia integration. Hu et al. (2025) introduced the “BOPPPS + blended teaching model” in a food biochemistry course. They integrated in a FC approach small private online course (SPOC) resources with in-class “Bridge-in, Objective/Outcome, Pre-assessment, Participatory Learning, Post-assessment, Summary” (BOPPPS) strategies. The results showed that, compared with the control group, the students had better performance scores and in-depth mastery of knowledge. Siqiang et al. (2024) found that merging a FC and the BOPPPS model also lifted outcomes.

Alwadei et al. (2020) examined the use of adaptive learning platforms (ALPs) to encourage interaction in a FC context. The study noted that across three student groups (face-to-face, summative ALP and formative ALP) test scores were highest in the group of students using the summative ALP. This curriculum design, using FC and ALP, has shown significant results in student learning. Buczek-Zawiła (2023) explored a blended phonetics course that improved outcomes through structured hybrid instruction using asynchronous, synchronous and partial

flipped learning elements. Das and Iyer (2024) implemented project-based learning in a so-called Volatile, Uncertain, Complex and Ambiguous (VUCA) environment, which promoted real-world engagement.

3.1.2. Assessment and feedback mechanisms

Assessment and feedback mechanisms were widely employed in blended courses to guide student learning, monitor progress, and strengthen self-regulation. Alwadei et al. (2020) demonstrated that adaptive learning platforms provided both formative and summative assessment opportunities, allowing students to receive personalized feedback while also linking performance to measurable outcomes. This dual role improved student performance and highlighted the importance of balancing diagnostic feedback with evaluative assessment. In a VR-integrated robotics lab, Antonelli et al. (2023) measured engagement and performance through task-based assessments embedded directly in the simulation. This design enabled instructors to capture real-time data on learners' interactions, ensuring that assessment was not separate from but rather an integral part of the learning process. Similarly, Bahri et al. (2020) showed how Moodle-based quizzes and feedback loops promoted self-regulated learning, as students received ongoing guidance that encouraged them to monitor their own understanding of physiology concepts. Astudillo et al. (2022) emphasized learner agency in hybrid transitions by tailoring assessment modes to student preferences, illustrating how flexibility in assessment can maintain engagement and fairness in times of shifting delivery formats. In medical education, He et al. (2024) provided evidence that structured, timely feedback embedded within blended clinical training improved practical performance, underscoring the role of feedback as a bridge between theoretical learning and professional practice.

3.1.3. Scaffolding learners' progress

Several strategies for scaffolding learners' progress were employed to provide structured learning paths and support gradual skill development across diverse disciplines. Agustina et al. (2024) combined gamified environments with structured laboratory tasks, allowing learners to engage interactively while progressively building competence, thereby increasing motivation and sustaining engagement over time. Alwadei et al. (2020) implemented adaptive learning tools that offered both formative and summative support, tailoring feedback to individual learners' needs and promoting self-regulated learning in complex subject areas. In the domain of robotics, Antonelli et al. (2023) embedded virtual reality (VR) simulations with staged complexity, gradually increasing task difficulty to foster problem-solving skills while maintaining learner confidence. In health sciences education, Bahri et al. (2020) employed the Problem-Based Learning Reading Questioning Answering model through Moodle, guiding students stepwise through physiology concepts with structured prompts and reflection tasks, thereby enhancing conceptual understanding and retention. In language learning, Buczek-Zawiła (2023) structured linguistic exercises into incremental tasks that promoted knowledge retention and reduced failure rates, demonstrating the impact of scaffolding on long-term learning outcomes. Framework-based approaches such as BOPPPS were effectively applied by Siqiang et al. (2024)

and Zeng et al. (2021), which provided clear pre-class objectives, in-class practice, and post-class consolidation, supporting deliberate progression through course content.

Similarly, Olmedo-Torre et al. (2021) sequenced active tasks strategically to scaffold concept mastery, ensuring that learners could integrate and apply knowledge before advancing to more complex topics. In engineering and software education, Song (2022) implemented the Conceive-Design-Implement-Operate framework to stage software-testing projects, moving learners from foundational skills to integrative, collaborative tasks.

Pérez-Sanagustin et al. (2022) embedded self-regulated learning (SRL) prompts within the learning management system (LMS), strengthening the feedback loop by encouraging learners to reflect on progress and plan next steps. In addition, structured teaching models such as BOPPPS and team-based learning (Zeng et al., 2021; Siqiang et al., 2024) clarified assessment expectations, integrated checkpoints for feedback, and were associated with improved performance scores. A broader evidence base supports this: a meta-analysis of 44 studies by Li et al. (2024) showed that blended learning with the BOPPPS model produced higher achievement and satisfaction when assessment was frequent, transparent, and closely aligned with learning objectives.

3.1.4. Promotion of learner autonomy

A strong theme across many studies was the promotion of learner independence and responsibility for managing the learning process, a central benefit of well-designed blended environments.

Alwadei et al. (2020) demonstrated that adaptive learning systems encouraged self-paced review and individualized pathways, allowing learners to revisit challenging concepts as needed and progress once mastery was achieved. This adaptability not only supported weaker students but also prevented disengagement among advanced learners.

Antonelli et al. (2023) found that student engagement increased when learners were given control over their VR-based robotics experience. By deciding when and how to interact with simulation tasks, students could regulate the pace of their learning, which strengthened their sense of ownership and motivation. Similarly, Bahri et al. (2020) validated Moodle-based self-paced tools, showing that students benefited from being able to navigate complex physiology concepts at their own rhythm while still receiving structured guidance.

From a different perspective, Buczek-Zawiła (2023) noted that reduced failure rates in linguistics courses were linked to giving students the responsibility of managing their hybrid course load, which encouraged planning and consistent study habits. Astudillo et al. (2022) further highlighted that autonomy is not uniform across learners: students with a preference for online modalities reported greater independence, whereas those favoring face-to-face settings often relied more on instructor guidance. This underscores the importance of designing blended practices that can accommodate diverse levels of learner readiness for autonomy.

Lin and Sun (2024) emphasized structuring synchronous time around learner activity and control rather than instructor-led transmission. Their findings suggest that shifting the classroom dynamic toward learner responsibility - through collaborative tasks, peer teaching, and guided inquiry - creates stronger engagement. Scott et al. (2020) reinforced this view by embedding self-assessment and goal-setting exercises in blended writing courses, which cultivated metacognitive awareness and responsibility for progress. Finally, Kritzinger et al. (2021) showed that a carefully staged blended design in first-year biology enabled students to engage in independent study while still maintaining high pass rates. By balancing autonomy with structured scaffolding, the design supported novice learners in gradually developing self-directed learning skills.

3.1.5. Collaborative and social learning

Social learning principles were integrated into blended designs through online discussion forums, group projects, and peer feedback, demonstrating the centrality of collaboration in blended practices. Agustina et al. (2024) used Gather Town, a gamified virtual environment, to replicate lab-based collaboration. This allowed students to interact synchronously in small groups, simulating the dynamics of physical lab work while benefiting from the flexibility of digital spaces. Ciolacu et al. (2022) implemented Agile project management methods, enabling students to collaborate virtually in structured cycles of planning, feedback, and iteration. This design helped learners develop communication and teamwork skills.

Jin (2024) provided evidence from a cross-cultural, competency-based English pedagogy. Learners engaged in peer exchanges that improved intercultural communication, participation, and collaborative engagement. Similarly, Pertuz et al. (2023) and Vo et al. (2020) described peer-supported learning models in engineering and across both hard and soft sciences, showing how structured peer mentoring and cooperative projects fostered deeper understanding and increased persistence in blended courses.

At the institutional level, Yilmaz et al. (2022) identified faculty-development enablers that supported instructors in designing collaborative activities, highlighting that effective collaborative learning in blended contexts requires not only student participation but also faculty capacity to facilitate group dynamics. Scott et al. (2020) integrated peer review and feedback cycles in blended writing courses, which strengthened students' metacognitive awareness and improved writing quality. Likewise, Olmedo-Torre et al. (2021) embedded peer collaboration into instructional design tasks, which enhanced concept mastery.

Industry-oriented approaches further reinforced the value of collaboration. Ciolacu et al. (2022), through Agile-oriented digital innovation projects, and Song (2022), via the Conceive-Design-Implement-Operate framework, both emphasized industry-style team projects. These projects required learners to collaboratively solve complex problems, distribute roles, and deliver products under real-world constraints, thereby preparing students for collaborative professional environments while embedding teamwork as a core learning outcome.

3.1.6. Alignment in courses and curricula

Alignment is a critical factor for the effectiveness of courses and programmes. When objectives, activities, and assessments are closely connected, learners experience a coherent trajectory that reinforces intended outcomes across online and face-to-face components. Well-aligned blended curricula ensure that technology integration serves pedagogical goals (Helsa et al., 2023), that learning activities manage cognitive load effectively (Müller & Wulf, 2024), and that students understand the relevance of each task to their overall learning outcomes (Yorganci, 2020). Instructional alignment also fosters predictability and consistency, making it easier for students to navigate complex blends of digital and in-person delivery (Müller et al., 2023). Moreover, alignment that is responsive to learner characteristics (Sharma et al., 2020) increases inclusivity, ensuring that diverse student groups can benefit from blended education designs.

Helsa et al. (2023) proposed a TPACK-based hybrid model for developing computational thinking in mathematics. By explicitly aligning technological tools with pedagogical strategies and disciplinary content, their design ensured that the use of technology was not superficial but directly supported mathematical problem-solving objectives.

In management education, Müller & Wulf (2021, 2024) provided evidence-informed designs showing the impact of explicit instructional alignment. Their 2021 study focused on curriculum structures that connect case-based learning, assessment tasks, and course objectives, ensuring coherence across modalities.

In their 2024 study, they advanced this by applying cognitive load theory, demonstrating how careful alignment of digital and in-person components reduces extraneous cognitive load, helping learners focus on the essential tasks and thereby improving performance in blended contexts. Building on this, Müller et al. (2023) analyzed blended courses within a flexible learning program and identified why some designs were more effective than others. Their findings suggested that courses with clearer instructional alignment between objectives, delivery, and assessment were perceived as more coherent, yielded higher satisfaction, and supported more consistent achievement compared to those that relied on ad hoc or loosely structured blends.

3.1.7. Motivational design and inclusive practices

Agustina et al. (2024) explored gamified learning spaces to enhance engagement in science courses. Their study demonstrated that introducing points, badges, and narrative structures not only made laboratory activities more appealing but also fostered sustained motivation by breaking complex tasks into incremental, rewarding challenges.

Gamification was thus shown to increase persistence in blended environments, particularly when students had to navigate demanding practical tasks.

Antonelli et al. (2023) integrated virtual reality (VR) into robotics education, catering to diverse learning needs by offering students immersive, manipulable environments in which to experiment. The VR-based design accommodated students with varying levels of prior knowledge by scaffolding tasks in a staged manner, allowing learners to progress at their own

pace. Their findings suggested that inclusive use of immersive technologies can broaden participation, particularly in STEM domains where abstract concepts can be a barrier.

Espada-Chavarria et al. (2023) explicitly grounded their blended approach in Universal Design for Learning (UDL) principles. By diversifying modes of representation (visual, textual, auditory), engagement (choice of tasks, adaptive pacing), and expression (multiple ways to demonstrate knowledge), they increased access for learners with different abilities and learning preferences. Their results highlight how UDL provides a systematic framework for inclusive blended course design.

Jin (2024) demonstrated how a data-driven blended pedagogy improved students' intercultural communication skills. The design included culturally responsive materials, iterative feedback loops, and blended opportunities for cross-cultural exchange. This approach emphasized not only language competence but also inclusivity through the recognition and integration of diverse cultural perspectives.

Astudillo et al. (2022) examined learner preferences and access issues in hybrid courses during transitional phases of COVID-19 teaching. Their findings revealed significant differences in motivation and participation between students who preferred online versus face-to-face modalities, emphasizing the importance of offering flexible structures and equitable access to both modes in blended design. Similarly, Sharma et al. (2020) aligned programming pedagogy in Information Systems with learner characteristics, recognizing that instructional design had to take into account not only the sequencing of content and assessments but also the backgrounds and needs of learners in order to achieve intended outcomes.

Suyan and Goh (2023) analysed engagement factors in a blended English task-based learning environment. They found that student motivation was shaped not only by instructional quality but also by contextual factors such as perceived relevance of tasks, opportunities for autonomy, and the degree of support provided. Their study underscores that motivational design is not one-dimensional but rather a balance between structure, flexibility, and meaningful content.

3.1.8. Real-world relevance

Ma and Lee (2021) applied the ARCS model (Attention, Relevance, Confidence, Satisfaction) in workplace learning contexts, using blended strategies to connect instructional activities with learners' professional settings. Their study showed that explicitly linking learning activities to workplace challenges enhanced relevance, which in turn boosted motivation and satisfaction. In particular, the relevance component of ARCS proved critical in blended environments. Das and Iyer (2024) designed hybrid courses around real-life learning. Students were required to collaborate on authentic workplace-style projects that demanded problem-solving, communication, and teamwork.

Their findings showed that when learners saw direct links between course tasks and industry practices, engagement and motivation increased substantially. Students also reported a stronger sense of preparedness for professional work.

Buczek-Zawiła (2023) redesigned phonetics instruction for applied professional communication. Instead of focusing exclusively on theoretical linguistic features, the blended course included workplace-oriented tasks such as preparing presentations, practicing professional interviews, and simulating communication challenges. This approach not only improved retention of linguistic knowledge but also reduced failure rates by highlighting the practical value of course content in real-world careers.

Agile collaboration methodologies were incorporated in Ciolacu et al.'s (2022) blended digital innovation courses. Students worked in small, industry-style teams to develop solutions for engineering problems. By mirroring real-world workplace practices - including iterative cycles, role distribution, and collaborative decision-making - the design equipped students with transferable skills in teamwork, leadership, and problem-solving, while also reinforcing course content through authentic application.

Astudillo et al. (2022) studied how hybrid education formats could better meet workplace expectations. They observed that students valued flexible access to materials and synchronous interactions when these mirrored professional contexts in which remote collaboration and hybrid work are increasingly common. Their findings suggested that blended courses preparing students for the hybrid workplace can foster both technical and adaptive skills, aligning academic practices with professional realities.

3.1.9. Tool integration

Digital tools in blended learning environments should be pedagogically aligned, adaptive, and feedback-rich, functioning as scaffolds for active, authentic, and SRL rather than as passive content delivery systems.

Bahri et al. (2020) showed how an LMS can serve as both a content delivery platform and a formative tool for knowledge reinforcement in physiology courses. They employed Moodle's functionalities for continuous feedback, automated testing, and scaffolded learning. In Guo et al.'s (2024) FC digital tools supported pre-class preparation and in-class active learning. These included: video lectures, collaborative online whiteboards and reflective journals. Agustina et al. (2024) demonstrated how augmented reality and gamified virtual spaces could enrich laboratory-based instruction. By combining interactive simulations with playful elements, students developed procedural knowledge, while simultaneously improving engagement and motivation. Antonelli et al. (2023) integrated VR-based robotics labs, allowing learners to experiment with robotic systems in immersive environments which supported progressive skill development and enhanced student agency, since learners could manipulate complex systems without the cost or risk associated with physical labs. Deng et al. (2022) used digital clinical case simulations. Students reported that the technology-based design improved their ability to transfer knowledge into professional contexts.

Astudillo et al. (2022) mapped learner preferences across online and offline modalities. Their work emphasized that tool selection should not be driven solely by institutional availability, but by learner needs and context, revealing how modality alignment affects motivation and

autonomy. Alwadei et al. (2020) used an adaptive learning platform that personalized tasks based on learners' progress. Results indicated significant gains in both formative and summative performance, highlighting the value of adaptive systems in tailoring content to individual needs within blended designs. Sharma et al. (2020) discussed tool choices in programming courses. They found that the effectiveness of blended pedagogy depends on selecting tools that balance usability with authentic practice. They emphasized that tool integration must consider both technical constraints and learner readiness. Pérez-Sanagustin et al. (2022) developed a Moodle plugin that embedded self-regulated learning (SRL) prompts for encouraging learners to reflect on goals, strategies, and progress. The tool improved SRL behaviors and demonstrated how LMS extensions can go beyond content delivery to actively shape learning processes.

Lu et al. (2024) analysed institutional-level MOOC/SPOC implementation, identifying how scaling digital platforms requires aligning pedagogy with institutional strategy. Their study emphasized challenges in maintaining quality and engagement when digital courses are deployed across large cohorts. Zappatore et al. (2022) designed a large-scale SimMOOC, which simulated cybersecurity scenarios for thousands of learners. This work illustrated the potential of simulation-based MOOCs to develop applied problem-solving skills at scale, while demonstrating the logistical and pedagogical challenges of designing such environments. Dong et al. (2021) outlined a SPOC-based design path, emphasizing how small private online courses (SPOCs) could provide more personalized, controlled, and effective experiences than traditional MOOCs.

Qi and Huang (2024) showed how learning analytics can improve teaching quality by identifying bottlenecks in learner progress and informing data-driven teaching interventions. Their study highlighted the potential of analytics as a feedback loop not only for learners, but also for instructors.

3.1.10. Model-driven blended designs

Blended learning environments should be designed through coherent, model-driven frameworks that integrate pedagogical theory with instructional design processes, ensuring intentional sequencing, learner support, contextual adaptation, and alignment across modalities. Model-driven blended design draws on both pedagogical models and instructional design models to structure effective learning experiences.

Pedagogical models provide the theoretical foundation for how learning occurs, describing the roles of teachers and learners, the nature of knowledge, and the strategies that foster engagement, interaction, and knowledge construction. In contrast, instructional design models offer systematic, step-by-step processes for planning, sequencing, and evaluating learning activities and resources. While pedagogical models inform the guiding principles that shape a learning approach, instructional design models translate these principles into concrete design decisions and practical course structures. Together, they form a complementary framework for designing clear, intentional, and evidence-informed blended teaching environments.

Flipped classroom

The FC can be characterized as an active learning approach. This method has been extensively documented in the literature. Commonly referred to as a rotational type of blended practices (Staker & Horn, 2012), it is also known as the "inverted classroom". This approach combines online and in-person activities with the aim of improving student engagement and enhancing deeper learning (Hyttinen & Suhonen, 2022;). By transferring content delivery to outside class time, FCs enable more interactive and collaborative learning experiences during face-to-face sessions (Burke & Fedorek, 2017). Results showed improved conceptual understanding and engagement, with the flipped design helping students actively construct knowledge rather than passively receive it.

Figure 5:
Flipped classroom design (from Nedeva et al., 2019)

Guo et al. (2024) integrated a FC combined with design-thinking in histology and embryology, where students engaged with digital pre-class resources (videos, quizzes) and then applied knowledge during in-class problem-solving. The design-thinking cycle encouraged iterative reflection and innovation, extending the flipped model beyond knowledge transfer to higher-order reasoning. In the field of mathematics education, Yorganci (2020) grounded flipped learning in Merrill's First Principles of Instruction, showing that by structuring content delivery, practice, and application around a design model, students were better supported in engaging with abstract mathematical concepts.

Olmedo-Torre et al. (2021) used FC approaches in graphic engineering, structuring pre-class video lectures with in-class collaborative design activities. The model highlighted how discipline-specific adaptation of flipped learning is key: engineering students particularly benefited from combining visualization tasks with hands-on projects. Pertuz et al. (2023) applied a MOOC-based FC in engineering, where students used MOOC content for preparation and then engaged in in-person collaborative activities. Müller & Wulf (2021) used a flipped approach in management courses, combining pre-class digital lectures with interactive seminars. Their design emphasized cognitive activation and practical application, aligning business education with problem-based approaches.

ADDIE

Sharma et al. (2020) applied the *ADDIE* model in programming pedagogy. The structured phases (analysis, design, development, implementation, evaluation) helped create iterative improvements and ensured alignment between objectives, content, and assessment. This systematic approach supported both learner progression and course adaptability. Helsa et al. (2023) used *ADDIE* together with *TPACK* to create a hybrid model for mathematics education. This ensured that computational thinking skills were explicitly built into lessons, with *ADDIE* providing the iterative design process and *TPACK* guiding the integration of pedagogy and technology.

Blended BOPPPS

Li et al. (2024) conducted a meta-analysis showing that BOPPPS-based blended designs (Bridge-in, Objectives, Pre-assessment, Participatory learning, Post-assessment, and Summary, see Figure 6a) consistently improved student achievement and satisfaction. The structured nature of BOPPPS was particularly effective when aligned with blended assessment strategies. Siqiang et al. (2024) confirmed these findings in medical education, where BOPPPS clarified expectations and provided repeated cycles of engagement and feedback. Zeng et al. (2021) also demonstrated that BOPPPS in blended formats improved clarity of objectives, performance outcomes, and student motivation.

Figure 6a:
BOPPPS model phases (Li, 2017).

Figure 6b:
Blended instructional design based on BOPPPS model (Zeng, 2023).

Other models

According to Baldassarre et al. (2021), the design of a blended course should be guided by the six dimensions of e-learning proposed by Bellagente (2006), which provide a structured way to combine presence and distance in higher education. The six design options identified are:

1. Completely at a distance: courses delivered fully online.
2. Completely remote with tutor support: online delivery complemented with guidance from a tutor to sustain engagement and learning.
3. Mixed presence: distance with self-training at a distance – face-to-face sessions combined with autonomous online study.
4. Mixed presence: distance with complementary distance activities: in-person classes enhanced with online activities that extend or deepen learning.
5. Blended designs focused on flexible learning pathways: allowing students to adapt the balance of online and in-person learning according to their needs.
6. Blended designs that respond to specific training needs: tailoring modality choices to the characteristics of the subject matter or learner group.

From these options, Baldassarre et al. (2021) argued that an effective blended course:

- involves deliberate choices to optimise engagement and outcomes;
- must be designed around a needs analysis;
- is context-sensitive, flexible, and learner-focused;
- fosters student autonomy and interaction with both content and peers, with a tutor providing scaffolding and motivation, especially when distance learning elements dominate.

Similarly, Raviolo et al. (2021) contended a blended design requires its own logic and structure. It has not to be designed by simply transferring face-to-face teaching models into an online setting. Instead, they assert that its effectiveness depends on a few critical elements:

- Careful planning of teaching and learning activities: ensuring that the sequencing, pacing, and integration of online and in-person elements are purposeful rather than incidental.
- Strong tutoring systems: providing scaffolding, guidance, and ongoing support so that learners can navigate the complexity of blended environments.
- High-quality interaction with meaningful exchanges between educators and learners but also among peers.
- Responsiveness to student needs and expectations: recognising that learners enter blended courses with different backgrounds, levels of digital competence, and preferences for how they engage with learning materials.

This perspective is reinforced by Williams et al. (2022), who show that HEIs, especially in the wake of the COVID-19 pandemic, have demonstrated a growing capacity to design across multiple modalities. Their findings suggest that universities are more flexible than previously

assumed, and can move between face-to-face, remote, and hybrid formats when design principles are adaptive and forward-looking.

Some contributions emphasise design principles for time and space flexibility. Leinonen and Mäkelä (2022) propose five principles for hybrid environments, namely: ensuring access to tools, infrastructure and support, prioritising either synchronous online or onsite design, adopting a “less is more” approach, and paying attention to detail. These principles underscore the need for pragmatic, context-sensitive design that supports diverse learning preferences. Similarly, Jansone-Ratinka et al. (2023) extend these ideas into the domain of social and health care education, outlining principles such as student-centred learning, collaborative approaches, evidence-informed practice, assessment and feedback, and continuous professional development for staff.

Vo et al. (2020) applied the *Community of Inquiry* (CoI) framework across disciplines, showing how teaching presence, cognitive presence, and social presence structured student interaction and knowledge construction in blended courses. Yilmaz et al. (2022) emphasized *Universal Design for Learning* (UDL) principles, ensuring accessibility and inclusivity across diverse learner groups. Their work showed that applying UDL in blended settings increased student participation and reduced equity gaps.

Building on a state-of-the-art review (47 references) informed by the work of the French-speaking European collective Hy-Sup (Peraya et al., 2014) and conducted using the Traceable Human Experiment Design Research (THEDRE) methodology (Mandran, 2018), Martinet and colleagues (2023) propose the following definition of the “polysemic concept of hybridization” in French:

Hybridization is a coherent pedagogical combination of face-to-face sessions involving both teacher and students, and remote sessions - synchronous or asynchronous - supported by new technologies. Its purpose is to enhance the accessibility of educational programs by making them both more flexible and more tailored to learners' needs. Five parameters can be mobilized to varying degrees, depending on the designer's representations:

- 1. The articulation of activities within coherent pedagogical approaches, considering spatial and temporal dimensions according to pedagogical needs, context, and the constraints faced by all stakeholders;*
- 2. Educational support, materialized through tutorial and collaborative scenarios, associated with a strategic arrangement;*
- 3. Mediation through media, whereby pedagogical functions and resources (activities, materials) are designed for distance learning and contribute to mediation and the development of learner autonomy;*
- 4. The openness of the system, expressed in the degree of control over learning granted to students;*
- 5. Assessment and its design, encompassing all the defined spatio-temporal learning spaces.” (Martinet et al., 2023, p. 135)*

In continuation of this French-language definition, Martinet (2024) further developed his work through two proposals:

1. a design model specific to hybridisation called the GRHYD (Grid for Reading HYbridization Device), to address three types of hybridisation:
 - a. hybridisation of pathways (e.g. courses or modules),
 - b. teaching methods,
 - c. content.
2. a design model specific to hybridisation called the GRHYD (Grid for Reading HYbridization Device):
 - a. design the hybrid learning unit (by means of an interactive tool called the "hybridisation wheel", presented in the form of a circle made up of six axes, represented in the form of scales relating to one of the parameters identified by the author to characterise hybridisation).
 - b. conceive the 'meta-scenario' (spatio-temporal articulation of periods through pedagogical phases, which pre-structure the learning unit).
 - c. develop a detailed script for the teaching phases defined above.

However, despite the interest of this rare recent French-language European contribution, one of the major limitations of the methods and tools proposed in Martinet's work is that the sequence of three steps based on a succession of tools, requires that teachers be assisted by an expert such as an educational engineer.

Toolkits and guidelines for practice

Practical toolkits also play a role in shaping design. Young and Perović (2020) developed the "ABC Learning Design toolkit" (see <https://abc-ld.org/>), which is grounded in Laurillard's *Conversational Framework*. This approach enables rapid, pedagogically coherent course design through collaborative workshops that map out student learning activities.

In van Valkenburg et al. (2020), as well as Goeman and Dijkstra (2021) one retrieves a set of principles, guidelines and examples for practice when designing blended courses or programs.

3.2. What standards and frameworks exist for evaluating and improving the quality and maturity of blended learning practices in higher education?

Based on scientific, as well as grey and professional literature, several frameworks were identified for evaluating or improving the quality and maturity of blended practices in higher education². These span both policy-level instruments and practical evaluation models. There are technology-enhanced systems that provide dynamic, data-driven insights, next to statistical and survey methods that consider predominantly instructional components and learner satisfaction; and discipline-specific approaches which render evaluation sensitive to the distinctive goals of a field.

3.2.1. Quality assurance

Benson et al.'s 2024 systematic literature review examines quality assurance interventions within blended higher education. The authors' aim was to stimulate HEIs to incorporate evidence-informed QA activities.

The Context, Input, Process, Product (CIPP) evaluation model was adapted to create the Blended Teaching Quality Evaluation Scale (BTQES) in undergraduate nursing (Zhao et al., 2024). This tool ensures that course design, delivery processes, and outcomes are systematically evaluated. Its emphasis on both process (teaching, scaffolding, feedback) and product (student outcomes) demonstrates how quality evaluation moves beyond summative performance metrics. The validated Blended Learning Quality Assessment Scale (Panigrahi et al., 2024) foregrounds learner satisfaction and the alignment of learning outcomes with course design, ensuring that quality is not only measured through performance but also through learner perceptions and engagement.

Another strand is the development of technology-enhanced evaluation models, which harness advanced computational methods to refine how quality is measured. For example, Wang et al. (2023) introduced a deep learning-based teaching evaluation system that refines performance indicators by drawing directly on learner activity data. Rather than relying solely on static survey measures, this approach makes evaluation more dynamic and responsive to actual patterns of student engagement, allowing instructors and institutions to track quality in near real time. In a similar vein, Shi et al. (2023) developed an AI-driven quality model for blended English instruction. By analysing large datasets of learner interaction, the model was able to optimize course delivery and highlight where instructional adjustments were most needed.

Alongside these computational methods, more traditional statistical and survey-based approaches remain significant in blended practice evaluation. These underscore the centrality of the learner's perspective in evaluation by emphasizing learner satisfaction, transparency, and

² Some of the frameworks listed below predate 2020, although the articles referencing them were published within the past five years.

comparability. For example, [Ye and Wu \(2023\)](#) published a learner experience-based evaluation model for online and blended courses, validated through factor analysis. It includes five dimensions (course resources, course environment, learning interaction, learning support, emotional experience) and 17 indicators. [Wang et al. \(2024\)](#) introduced a *value assignment method* for blended physical education courses, which explicitly weighted evaluation criteria to show how different teaching activities contributed to overall quality. This statistical weighting method helped to clarify the relative importance of instructional elements that are often treated equally in conventional evaluations.

Similarly, [Zhang et al. \(2024\)](#) employed *satisfaction-based prioritization* to identify which elements most directly influenced student learning effectiveness. They developed a blended learning effect evaluation index system based on teaching organization and activities. Using the analytic hierarchy process, the model quantifies and weights evaluation indicators, overcoming earlier challenges of subjectivity. However, its intensive indexing and monitoring may face limited applicability in European contexts where concerns about over-assessment prevail.

Beyond individual course designs, broader evaluation, benchmarking and standards-based approaches exist. For example, [Luo et al. \(2024\)](#) developed a blended teaching evaluation system based on the CIPP model (Context, Input, Process, Product). The framework emphasizes holistic assessment of institutional environment, resource input, teaching process, and educational outcomes. Its strength lies in its practical adaptability and scientific grounding, though details of its application in HE remains unclear. [Sankey and Mishra \(2019\)](#) introduced a “Benchmarking Toolkit for Technology-Enabled Learning”, which provides institutions with a self-assessment framework covering 10 key areas. Similarly, official frameworks such as the “Statutory Quality Assurance Guidelines” in Ireland ([QQI, 2023](#)) and the “European Standards and Guidelines” ([ENQA, 2015; 2022](#)) outline national and continental approaches to quality assurance, increasingly including provisions for blended and digital learning environments. [Mahmud and Ismail \(2020\)](#) established another comprehensive quality framework. They adapted the five Sloan Consortium quality indicators (learning effectiveness, access, cost-effectiveness and institutional commitment, faculty satisfaction, student satisfaction) and integrated them with Key Success Indicators (KSIs). This multimodal approach provides institutions with standards that connect strategic leadership, faculty practices, and student experiences.

[Benson et al. \(2024\)](#) identified several frameworks for assessment and benchmarking in HE, with two deemed particularly relevant for blended practices:

- Quality Matters: A district or institutional rubric for evaluating the quality of online and blended courses based on a set of standards focused on design, instruction, and student engagement.
- Technology Enhanced Learning Accreditation Standards (ASCILITE, 2020): Standards developed to guide institutions in enhancing their technology-enabled learning offerings.

Finally, some evaluation models are discipline-specific, reflecting how evaluation cannot be one-size-fits-all but must remain sensitive to the pedagogical goals and practices of different fields.

Guo et al. (2021) proposed a practice-oriented blended teaching model for computer science. In this case, the quality of blended learning was measured not only in terms of content delivery but also in how effectively the design supported professional skill development. Similarly, Guo (2024) focused on innovation in English language teaching, analyzing how digital delivery reshaped instructional quality in response to learner needs. Makhachashvili & Semenist (2021) conducted a survey-based quality assessment of digital and blended learning across 14 Ukrainian universities in Oriental and European language programs during COVID-19 lockdowns. Their findings highlight socio-psychological challenges for students (motivation, adaptation) and technical/digital literacy challenges for faculty. While context-specific, the study underscores the importance of tailoring quality standards to disciplinary and regional realities.

3.2.2. Maturity assessment

The literature shows that maturity models in blended education are relatively rare. The EMBED (Van Valkenburg et al., 2020; Goeman et al., 2021; Goeman et al., 2022) is a comprehensive European framework that supports institutions in progressing from fragmented, ad-hoc blended practices to systematically embedded and strategic blended education. This framework takes a multi-level perspective. It is structured around maturity dimensions that cover both course, program and institutional perspectives. Each dimension has descriptors across multiple stages of maturity, enabling stakeholders to map their position and set development goals.

EMBED is to a certain extent complemented by Cappelli & Smithies' Blended Learning Model (2021). It is less a structured "ladder of maturity" and more a capacity-building model. It focuses specifically on institutional readiness and sustainable scaling of blended education. Instead of categorizing institutions into maturity stages, it places particular emphasis on strengthening capacities that enable blended practices to move beyond isolated pilots. Like EMBED Cappelli and Smithies (2021) is also an evidence-informed framework. It is structured around four core elements:

1. Environment: the institutional context, including policies, leadership, and digital systems;
2. Curriculum: the design coherence between online and face-to-face components,
3. Educators: the preparedness and support structures for faculty,
4. Learners: the support, engagement, and inclusion of students within blended initiatives.

Both the EMBED and the BLM are not just descriptive but actionable: they serve as self-assessment checklists, enabling institutions to gauge their current blended practices, identify gaps, and establish clear performance objectives to progress toward an "ideal" state. Through regular monitoring and iterative review, institutions can track their progress and maturity in delivering blended education.

4. Synthesis and recommendations

4.1. Components of effective blended courses and programs

4.1.1. INSIGHT 1. EMBED active learning

Active learning consistently emerged as a core principle of effective blended course design. Across the reviewed studies, approaches such as the flipped classroom and project-based learning were shown to improve student performance, while structured sequences and carefully selected materials ensured that learners remained engaged and able to achieve deeper processing and mastery.

To be effective, active learning in blended settings requires more than interactive techniques alone: it must be deliberately embedded into the course structure, aligning online and face-to-face activities, learning materials, and learner support. This alignment allows students to reflect, collaborate, and problem-solve across modalities, while self-assessment checkpoints help sustain autonomy and track progress.

In practice, active learning in blended education therefore relies on multi-modal, participatory learning sequences that balance interaction, structure, and flexibility to foster meaningful engagement and long-term learning outcomes.

4.1.2. INSIGHT 2. EMBED assessment and feedback

Assessment and feedback emerged as pivotal components of effective blended course design. The evidence showed that when assessment and feedback are intentionally embedded into blended education design, they enhance achievement, promote learner autonomy, and strengthen the overall coherence of the learning experience.

To be effective, assessment in blended contexts must be seamlessly integrated into the learning process. Rather than serving merely as tools to measure performance, they actively shape learning trajectories by guiding reflection, adaptation, and mastery. Across the reviewed studies, effective assessments were shown to provide timely feedback, enabling instructors to intervene early and learners to self-correct.

Formative and summative tasks should be directly aligned with learning objectives and activities, ensuring coherence and clarity for students. Transparent structures, such as BOPPPS, reduce ambiguity around expectations, while frequent low-stakes assessments sustain motivation and support self-regulation.

Adaptive technologies, including LMS-based quizzes and immersive simulations, further personalize the feedback process, offering learners immediate insights and strengthening engagement.

4.1.3. INSIGHT 3. EMBED scaffolding

Scaffolding plays a decisive role in shaping effective blended practices, with clear benefits for engagement, progression, and mastery of complex skills. Across the reviewed studies, effective scaffolding was shown to rely on staged pathways, structured sequences, and timely support, allowing learners to progress with confidence and achieve durable mastery of complex skills.

Effective scaffolding in blended contexts often combines online and face-to-face elements into carefully staged sequences. Gamified or incremental laboratory activities, for example, maintained learner motivation while gradually increasing complexity, while adaptive and formative tools provided timely, individualized feedback across modalities. In task- and problem-based designs, scaffolding guided learners through increasingly complex content, supporting retention, reducing failure rates, and fostering deeper conceptual understanding.

Framework-based approaches, such as BOPPPS, highlighted how pre-class preparation, active in-class engagement, and post-class consolidation can be systematically aligned to create predictable and supportive learning trajectories. When paired with collaborative and reflective activities, scaffolding ensured that learning was not only incremental but also active and applied.

4.1.4. INSIGHT 4. EMBED learner autonomy

Learner autonomy emerges as a powerful driver of motivation, engagement, and persistence in blended practices. By enabling students to adapt their learning trajectories to personal needs and circumstances, autonomy fosters deeper engagement with content, more efficient use of time, and the development of transferable self-regulation skills that extend beyond the classroom. Evidence shows that greater autonomy is associated with higher achievement and lower failure rates, as students take greater responsibility for mastering material.

However, the studies consistently caution that autonomy must be carefully balanced with structure and guidance. Without sufficient scaffolding, some learners - particularly those less confident with online modalities - may feel overwhelmed or disengaged. Effective blended designs therefore cultivate autonomy gradually, combining adaptive systems, staged pathways, and opportunities for reflection to ensure that independence grows alongside competence.

In practice, fostering learner autonomy in blended contexts means providing opportunities for self-paced progression and decision-making, embedding reflection and goal setting into task sequences, and aligning freedom with timely support. When autonomy is intentionally nurtured in this way, it enhances student agency while sustaining meaningful engagement and durable learning outcomes.

4.1.5. INSIGHT 5. EMBED collaborative and social learning

Collaborative and social learning plays a central role in enhancing engagement, understanding, and skill development within blended environments. By fostering interaction among peers, these approaches not only strengthen communication and critical thinking but also cultivate a sense of belonging that counteracts the isolation often associated with digital spaces.

The impact of collaboration is particularly pronounced in contexts that demand intercultural competence or peer-supported learning. Students benefit from diverse perspectives and problem-solving, which deepen conceptual understanding and broaden their capacity to work across differences.

Peer review practices further reinforce this effect, improving academic performance while honing learners' ability to critically evaluate and articulate knowledge. At the same time, sustaining high-quality collaboration requires deliberate instructional support. Faculty training and facilitation are essential to ensure that peer interactions remain meaningful, constructive, and inclusive.

In practice, this means embedding structured opportunities for collaboration and discussion, both synchronous and asynchronous, supported by digital tools that enable teamwork, peer feedback, and cross-cultural exchange. When designed intentionally, collaborative learning in blended contexts becomes a catalyst for both academic achievement and the development of lifelong interpersonal and professional skills.

4.1.6. INSIGHT 6. EMBED constructive and curriculum alignment

Constructive and curriculum alignment is fundamental to effective blended course design. Its impact is twofold: first, it improves learning outcomes by ensuring that objectives, activities, and assessments all pull in the same direction; second, it enhances learner satisfaction and engagement by providing transparent, coherent learning pathways. When alignment is missing, blended courses risk fragmentation, with students experiencing online and in-person activities as disjointed rather than complementary.

The reviewed studies highlighted that alignment across modalities strengthens both clarity and inclusivity. Explicitly linking digital and face-to-face components helped students perceive the blended environment as a unified whole, while careful sequencing of content reduced cognitive overload and promoted equitable participation. Effective alignment therefore does more than provide structure: it creates a pedagogical flow in which every component - objectives, tasks, and assessments - reinforces one another, guiding students progressively toward mastery.

In practice, constructive alignment in blended practices require deliberate design decisions: setting clear objectives, sequencing content with attention to cognitive load, and ensuring that each digital and in-person element directly contributes to the intended learning outcomes. This coherence makes the blended experience both meaningful and sustainable.

4.1.7. INSIGHT 7. EMBED motivational design and inclusive practices

Motivation and inclusivity are mutually reinforcing elements of successful blended course design. Learners are most engaged when activities are perceived as relevant, appropriately challenging, and responsive to their personal or cultural contexts. At the same time, inclusive practices ensure that all students, regardless of background, ability, or learning preference, can participate fully and meaningfully.

The evidence showed that motivational strategies such as gamification and immersive technologies sustain engagement by offering variety, novelty, and opportunities for agency. In parallel, inclusive frameworks such as UDL and culturally responsive pedagogy reduce barriers to participation and acknowledge diversity in learner needs. Crucially, motivation was highest when supportive structures, such as scaffolds, timely feedback, and flexible pacing, were combined with opportunities for autonomy, ensuring that students felt both guided and empowered.

Taken together, these findings highlight that inclusive motivational design is not an add-on but a cornerstone of blended education. By embedding UDL principles, offering choices in task types, modalities, and pacing, and fostering environments that validate diverse learner perspectives, educators can enhance persistence, prevent disengagement, and strengthen equity in participation.

4.1.8. INSIGHT 8. EMBED real-world relevance

Real-world relevance plays a decisive role in making blended education meaningful, engaging, and transferable. When learners perceive a direct connection between classroom activities and professional or societal contexts, both cognitive engagement (through challenging, authentic tasks) and affective engagement (through enjoyment and perceived value) are significantly enhanced.

Across the reviewed studies, embedding authentic, workplace-relevant activities into blended course design consistently improved learner motivation, knowledge retention, and satisfaction. Project-based and industry-inspired activities - often structured through Agile or collaborative models - helped students develop transferable skills in communication, teamwork, and problem-solving. These practices not only reinforced conceptual understanding but also fostered professional readiness by simulating the complexity of contemporary workplaces. The effect was particularly pronounced in preparing students for hybrid and digital work environments that demand collaboration across modalities.

Designing for real-world relevance means aligning blended education tasks with learners' professional aspirations, integrating authentic projects, and fostering collaborative problem-solving. By doing so, blended courses bridge theory and practice, increase employability, and cultivate learner confidence in applying skills beyond the classroom.

4.1.9. INSIGHT 9. EMBED tools as learning scaffolds, not containers

Technology extends far beyond its role as a medium of delivery; it functions as an enabler of blended pedagogy when tool usability, learner readiness and authentic practice are balanced. When used strategically they actively shape how students engage, reflect, and progress in their learning.

Across the reviewed studies, the integration of immersive technologies, adaptive platforms, learning analytics, and LMS extensions was shown to optimize student learning trajectories by fostering autonomy, relevance, and sustained engagement, while also enabling institutions to deliver blended education effectively and at scale.

The pedagogical impact of technology integration was evident across several dimensions. Scalability and accessibility were enhanced through MOOCs, SPOCs, and other digital platforms, enabling institutions to reach large and diverse cohorts without sacrificing quality. Authenticity and application were strengthened through VR, AR, and simulation-based tools, which mirrored real-world contexts and made abstract concepts tangible. Personalization and autonomy were supported by adaptive systems and self-regulated learning tools, which empowered learners to progress at their own pace while receiving timely, targeted feedback. At the same time, engagement and motivation increased when gamification and scenario-based designs created immersive and interactive environments. Finally, data-informed teaching became possible through analytics tools that enabled instructors to identify learner challenges early and adapt teaching strategies accordingly.

4.1.10. INSIGHT 10. EMBED model-driven coherence

Effective design is not a matter of technological substitution but of pedagogical rethinking. It requires continuous alignment between learning theory, activity sequencing, modalities, and support structures, while ensuring flexibility to adapt to feedback and institutional constraints.

In this context, agile design approaches (Beck et al., 2001) are particularly valuable, as they promote iterative cycles of planning, implementation, reflection, and refinement. By combining structure with adaptability, agile methods help educators respond quickly to learner needs and institutional realities, making blended practices both rigorous and responsive. Frameworks and toolkits are therefore central: they provide educators with structured pathways for course design, while also enabling the dialogue - among staff and between teachers and students - that lies at the heart of successful blended education.

According to Basque and colleagues (2010), despite the diversity of practices and methods in the design of learning environments, two overarching approaches can be distinguished, irrespective of the type of environment targeted or the learning theories privileged: the design process may be either problem-centred (analytical approach) or solution-centred (pragmatic approach). The *analytical approach* follows a systematic methodology often referred to by the acronym ADDIE, the five phases of which were already present in the earliest instructional design methods (Branson et al., 1975) in response to a request from the US Army, to hasten production of training materials by persons having less than a thorough background in instructional design. Numerous subsequent methods have incorporated these phases with slight

variations, placing particular emphasis on the precise definition of the training or learning problem to be addressed prior to engaging in the development of a solution. In contrast, the *pragmatic approach* is solution-focused and relies on prototyping. A preliminary version of the learning environment is created, followed by successive iterations of parts or the whole. This continues until stakeholders are satisfied with the final solution. The first prototype is produced quickly, after only a brief problem analysis. It is then improved step by step through ongoing formative evaluation. Prototypes help specify the needs of sponsors and users, who actively take part in the process. They also support communication and build consensus about the learning environment.

For online learning, Rizal and colleagues (2022) applied the Successive Approximation Model (SAM, Allen & Sites, 2012) to design a Microlearning-Based Model in English Language Learning. SAM is an iterative framework to designing and building learner-centred learning, notably for instructional design that emphasizes early prototyping, frequent feedback, and continuous improvement. Ridulme and colleagues (2023) confirm that SAM is an alternative and practical response to the limitations of linear models like ADDIE. The authors highlight that SAM is particularly well suited for design, especially when it comes to quickly testing an initial functional prototype with the users involved in designing a training programme.

The scientific evidence showed that using or adapting models helps to establish blended arrangements. When combined, these models allow educators to align course components with discipline-specific needs, ensuring both coherence and responsiveness. Beyond technical considerations, their effectiveness depends on deliberate attention to the interplay of modalities - presence versus distance, synchronous versus asynchronous, and individual versus group work - and on their alignment with institutional structures and learner needs.

The reviewed studies illustrate that models are not abstract theories but practical guides that shape how blended practices unfold in higher education. Their impact can be seen across five dimensions:

1. Providing structure and coherence: Frameworks such as ADDIE and BOPPPS ensure systematic progression and clear alignment between objectives, content, and assessment.
2. Supporting discipline-specific needs: Adaptations of the flipped classroom in mathematics, engineering, and management illustrate how models must be contextualized to domain knowledge and learner practices.
3. Enhancing engagement and interaction: The CoI framework and gamified approaches foster collaboration, motivation, and stronger social presence.
4. Promoting inclusivity and accessibility: UDL principles ensure that technology-enhanced learning reaches diverse learners and minimizes participation barriers.
5. Balancing scalability and personalization: MOOC-based flipped models demonstrate how large-scale resources can be tailored to smaller, more personalized environments.

Professional and grey literature reinforce these findings by converging on several shared insights: effective blended course design requires a clear pedagogical framework, careful

balancing of coherence and flexibility, and strong student-centredness. Some approaches emphasize evidence-informed indicators, while others offer pragmatic heuristics or rapid toolkits, but the common recognition is that blended practices are a complex educational design challenge. Its success depends on the active engagement of students and faculty, not only in terms of access and competences, but also in aligning tools and delivery modes with pedagogical intent. Without intentional integration, blended practices risk remaining superficial - whereas with thoughtful design, it becomes a catalyst for deep learning and student satisfaction.

4.2. Elements of proven QA/MA practices

4.2.1. A dual focus: course-level quality and institutional maturity

A growing body of research literature has developed models, standards, and frameworks to evaluate and enhance the quality and maturity of blended practices. These approaches vary in their conceptual orientation, methodological tools, and geographical focus but collectively highlight two aspects of current evaluation:

- (2) the multidimensional nature of QA in blended education - spanning strategic, pedagogical, and experiential dimensions;
- (2) how technology itself has become a driver of evaluation in blended higher education, moving beyond survey-based quality checks to computational and dynamic approaches.

Most existing QA mechanisms in blended education operate at the course level, with an emphasis on learner satisfaction, instructional design quality, and technology-enhanced evaluation. Increasingly, analytics and AI-driven tools are being deployed to create real-time feedback loops, enabling adaptive, personalized, and data-informed evaluation.

While these mechanisms improve responsiveness, they remain insufficient on their own. Sustainable digital transformation requires linking course-level quality to institutional strategies and maturity models. This dual approach, balancing micro-level improvement with macro-level maturity, is critical to ensure blended education develops from scattered innovations into coherent, institution-wide transformation.

4.2.2. Towards CQI in the European blended higher education ecosystem

Blended higher education should not be understood as a collection of isolated courses but as a dynamic ecosystem composed of interdependent layers - pedagogical, technological, human, and organizational - that together shape the learner experience.

The studies highlighted the urgent need to move beyond fragmented QA processes and towards comprehensive, systemic approaches that embed continuous quality improvement (CQI) across all levels of the institution (Goeman et al., 2021; Cappelli & Smithies, 2021; Benson et al., 2024; Bidarra et al., 2024).

The development of blended ecosystems depends on the interplay between two complementary approaches (Bidarra et al., 2024):

- *Innovation policy (top-down)*: driven by leadership, strategic priorities, and regulatory frameworks that support the adoption of digital tools, innovative pedagogy, and quality monitoring.
- *Digital transformation (bottom-up)*: emerging from faculty creativity, student initiatives, and local experimentation that generate new ways of teaching and learning.

Continuous improvement requires connecting these approaches: institutional strategies must provide the conditions for innovation to flourish, while local practices must inform and refine policy development.

Pedagogical layer (course and programme design):

- At the heart of the ecosystem lies the pedagogical design of courses and programmes. Effective blended practices require constructive alignment of learning outcomes, activities, and assessments across modalities.
- A mature ecosystem depends on shared design principles and structured feedback cycles to continuously refine coherence across digital and in-person components.

Technological layer (infrastructure and tools):

- Blended education is underpinned by technological systems, including learning management systems (LMS), synchronous and asynchronous communication tools, and increasingly, learning analytics and AI. These infrastructures enable both teaching innovation and large-scale participation.
- System maturity requires interoperability, equitable access, and the systematic use of analytics for informed decision-making.

Human layer (faculty, students, and support staff):

- Ecosystem sustainability relies on the people who design, deliver, and engage in blended practices. Faculty require professional development to gain digital and pedagogical capacity.
- Investment in capacity building across all stakeholder groups is essential, with emphasis on professional learning communities, peer support, and inclusive student engagement.

Organizational layer (strategy, policy, and quality culture):

- At the institutional level, strategic vision, policy coherence, and infrastructure investments shape the sustainability of blended practices. Institutions that rely on ad-hoc adoption risk fragmentation, whereas those embedding blended practices into strategic planning, funding allocations, and QA systems achieve more consistent results.
- Establishing a quality culture is crucial. This involves adopting maturity models and integrating systematic evaluation tools to create long-term coherence across blended education offerings.

Ecosystem dynamics and feedback loops

- Blended ecosystems are characterised by strong interdependencies. Pedagogical design influences technological requirements, while technology adoption shapes faculty readiness and student experiences. Institutional strategies provide resources and frameworks, but they depend on faculty buy-in and student engagement. Evaluation mechanisms, in turn, generate feedback that informs redesign, training, and policy updates. Improvements in one layer ripple through the system, while weaknesses can create systemic bottlenecks.
- For example, a well-designed course may fail if technological infrastructure is insufficient, or institutional ambitions may falter without faculty buy-in.
- Quality assurance must be conceptualised as a dynamic feedback system, integrating standards, analytics, and context-sensitive evaluation tools to continuously refine practices at both micro (course) and macro (institutional) levels.

Each of them has their strengths:

- Standards and benchmarks: may be compared and aligned with external expectations
- Evaluation models and instruments: enable strong quality assessment at the local levels
- Technology-enhanced QA and analytics: enable continuous, data-driven feedback
- Discipline-sensitive models: tailor quality approaches to specific contexts
- Maturity assessment tools: monitor institutional capability building and long-term embedding
-

By integrating these elements, HEIs can establish a holistic and multi-level quality framework that balances agility in course design with strategic alignment at the organizational level.

4.3. Critical reflections and suggestions for further research

The results from analysing 40+ scientific papers reveal both widely adopted strategies and important gaps in terminology and practice.

In many cases, design principles for blended courses and programs were implied rather than formally defined, and when named, they varied widely in terminology and scope. Collaboration, for example, ranged from asynchronous discussion boards (Sosa Díaz et al., 2021) to industry-linked project teams (Ciolacu et al., 2022), with limited cross-referencing or theoretical anchoring. While active learning could refer to short in-class discussions (Sosa Díaz et al., 2021) in one study to fully immersive, problem-based projects in another (Das & Iyer, 2024). This inconsistency not only limits comparability but also highlights the absence of a widely accepted “blueprint” for institutions wishing to develop blended practices. Without a shared taxonomy, institutions risk reinventing approaches in isolation, potentially overlooking proven strategies or misapplying principles in ways that reduce their effectiveness.

When the design principles are considered alongside the instructional models identified in this review, several patterns emerge that help explain both the strengths and the fragmentation in current blended practices. This flexibility enables creativity and responsiveness, but it also creates challenges for evaluation and replication. Without explicit links between principles and models, implementation risks becoming ad-hoc, with principles applied inconsistently and models adapted without clear evidence of impact.

Two insights emerge:

1. Design principles without models risk being vague, while models without design principles run the risk of being too rigid. Effective blended courses and programs appear strongest when both design principles and models are aligned.
2. Adaptation is inevitable but should be evidence-informed. Modifications to design models should be documented and evaluated so that their successes and limitations can be shared across different contexts.

Together, these patterns show that while the field is rich in experimentation, it still lacks the coherent frameworks and shared vocabulary necessary to translate promising local practices into scalable, evidence-informed strategies.

In addition to these conceptual and methodological inconsistencies, the literature reveals several underlying tensions that show the need for more critical attention. Although flexibility is widely cited as a key advantage of blended and hybrid arrangements, multiple studies suggest that increased flexibility often comes with a higher workload for both instructors and students, particularly in relation to coordinating multimodal activities, providing continuous support, and sustaining engagement across formats. Moreover, the growing reliance on digital tools raises the risk of technology choices driving pedagogical decisions rather than the other way around, resulting in designs that may be innovative but not pedagogically coherent. Finally, persistent equity gaps in digital participation remain a structural challenge: differences in access, digital competence, and familiarity with online learning environments continue to shape learners' experiences and outcomes. Addressing these tensions requires research that not only documents successful designs but also examines the conditions under which flexibility becomes burdensome, technology becomes over-prescriptive, and digital participation becomes uneven.

While adaptable to various higher education contexts, the application of evaluation frameworks was inconsistent, serving in some cases as a formative course evaluation tool and in others as a summative program review instrument. Some evaluation practices or tools were locally developed and lacked cross-context validation, limiting generalizability and cross-institutional benchmarking. This gap points to an underdeveloped layer of strategic planning in blended education, one that bridges individual course quality with long-term institutional capability.

Across both research foci, a clear pattern emerged: there is no integrated framework that aligns pedagogical design principles with institutional evaluation and maturity planning. This absence leaves institutions without a clear roadmap for scaling blended education beyond isolated initiatives. Compounding this gap is the inconsistency in terminology across studies (Sosa Díaz

et al., 2021; Vo et al., 2020). Without standardized terminology, the field risks fragmentation and missed opportunities for cross-institutional learning.

Several studies reflected a shift from static digital content toward intelligent, data-driven systems. AI-based grading (Shi et al., 2023), neural network evaluation of instructional quality (Zhao et al., 2024), and predictive learning analytics dashboards (Guo et al., 2024) show potential for personalizing instruction and enabling real-time pedagogical decision-making. However, none of the reviewed studies examined ethical safeguards, student perceptions of AI systems, or transparency in data use – an important oversight given the sensitivity of educational data.

There is a need for further research to establish the current trends and statistics regarding the uptake of blended practices in higher education within the EU. To our knowledge, anno 2025, no specific statistical data exist concerning the adoption of blended education, teaching and learning in the EHEA.

The synthesis process revealed three overarching limitations in existing literature. First, there is no universally agreed-upon definition of core terms such as “blended learning,” “hybrid,” or “flipped classroom,” leading to inconsistencies in both research design and reporting. Second, the formulation of design principles often lacks theoretical clarity, making it difficult to understand the intended scope or expected outcomes of a given principle. Third, quality evaluation frameworks are rarely validated across different contexts, meaning their reliability and applicability remain uncertain outside of their original development setting.

This review also faced limitations of its own. Despite an extensive search strategy, the identification of relevant literature was challenging due to inconsistent terminology and indexing practices, which may have led to the exclusion of relevant studies. Although several potentially relevant studies were identified, those that were non-peer-reviewed or methodologically incomplete could not be included, potentially narrowing the scope of available evidence.

Therefore, to advance the field, three priority areas for research and practice are proposed:

1. **Develop theoretical consistency:** Both scholars and practitioners would benefit from a common framework that demarcates key concepts. It would allow for clearer cross study comparison and provide institutions with a replicable blueprint for blended education and continuous quality improvement. In the context of EMBED+ an international Delphi study will be conducted to establish consensus about definitions and standards for the new model. Likewise, drawing on contributions from experts the terminology about design principles, QA and MA could be set.
2. **Validate designs, QA and MA tools in different HE contexts:** A series of promising frameworks have been developed for specific courses, programs, institutions or regions but remain untested elsewhere. Multi-site and multimethod studies could pilot these tools in diverse geographic and institutional contexts, evaluating their reliability, cultural adaptability, and predictive value for student outcomes.

3. Conduct ethically grounded research on AI-enhanced blended environments in HE: Given the rapid adoption of AI and learning analytics, research should not only measure their pedagogical impact but also investigate governance, transparency, and bias. For example, a longitudinal study could track the effects of AI-driven feedback systems on learner autonomy and performance while examining students' perceptions of fairness and data use.

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